

Aromatic oil composition and microstructures of some Indian cultivars of *Cuminum cyminum* L. in raw and roasted condition

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Manuscript received 24 June 2011, revised 10 May 2012, accepted 14 May 2012

Abstract : The aromatic oil is extracted from three cultivars of cumin grown in different regions of India by simple way of solvent extraction process using HPLC grade petroleum ether (boiling point range 40–60 °C). The composition of extracted oil is analyzed by Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry in raw and roasted condition. It is found that in case of three cultivars some new compounds are generated during roasting presumably due to Maillard reaction and they are different in percentage and composition. GCMS study reveals that hairy cumin variety of Rajasthan is enriched with various compounds of essential oil than other two varieties. The proportion percent of some compounds Alphapinene (1.31%), cumene (16.18%), careen (27%), Alpha-phellandrene (18%) and coumarin (4.2%) in raw hairy cumin are higher than other two cultivars of Rajasthan and West Bengal respectively. These percent compositions are changed in roasted condition. The micro morphological characters when viewed under scanning electron microscope show some differences in seed structures and oil secretory parts between both raw and roasted seeds. The papillose hairs and assemblage of canals tend to become stiff in the roasted materials than the raw ones. The structures of each seeds of the particular cultivars indicate a kind of character-specificity. A correlation of GCMS and SEM study have been established which may enable to identify the superior quality seeds.

Keywords : Cumin, aroma, GCMS, SEM.

Introduction

Seeds of *Cuminum cyminum* L. commonly known as cumin constitute one of the popular spices of Apiaceae family. Cumin is mostly cultivated spice in countries like Iran, China, Japan, India and Russia¹. In India cumin is cultivated in some states having rich silt loamy soil except the states of eastern region (West Bengal) where initiatives are taken to produce the crop on alluvial soil. Generally cumin seed producing states are Rajasthan, Gujarat, Tamilnadu and Maharashtra. It is evident that these states have favorable and ecological climatic conditions. Cumin seeds are an export commodity and can earn significant amount of foreign exchange². Cumin seeds, both raw and roasted, are used to impart the distinct aroma in food products as spices. Cumin is widely used for its therapeutic properties like antistomachic, di-

gestive, carminative agent and has possible effects as antioxidant³ and anticancerous⁴. The aroma compounds of cumin are made up of organic molecules like benzene derivatives⁵, alcohol, aldehydes and terpenes⁶. During roasting of cumin seed, Maillard reaction⁷ usually takes place and the roasted cumin changes its color to deep brown and composition⁸ of the potentially important odorants. Roasting causes the formation of new molecule which adds a distinctive odor and flavor to the roasted spice. These aroma molecules present in cumin are not fully characterized which are responsible for the full range of flavors; moreover the characterization of Maillard reaction products has to be critically examined. Our olfactory system can detect the presence of flavor but fails to identify the molecular nature. Instrumental tools like GCMS⁹ are frequently used for characterization of the com-

pounds¹⁰. Surface study by scanning electron microscopy¹¹ is used to differentiate between the varieties of the raw seeds. Family Apiaceae has unique feature of ornamentation on the seed surface area. Only SEM can reveal details due to its high resolution power¹². GCMS and SEM techniques together can be exclusively utilized in the characterization of aromatic oil composition and the seed structure respectively for each particular cultivar.

Results and discussion

The agro climatic factors of the western part of India are favorable for the growth of the high acreage yield of cumin seeds as well as their quality in terms of both aromatic oil content and composition. In this study the collected single cultivar of West Bengal is also analyzed for the improvement of the cultivation in future. The flavor profile of the three cultivars in raw and roasted condition are summarized in three tables and the chromatograms clearly show some dissimilarities in the proportion of the constituents between the cultivars. The compounds have been identified in this study with the comparison of the standards and authentic literature references^{13,14}.

Comparing three cultivars of cumin it is clear that Hairy cumin of Rajasthan is one of the desirable varieties based on the aromatic oil content. 22 compounds have been identified from the essential oil of this cultivar. Monoterpenes are present in the essential oil of three cultivars whereas, GCMS result supports that Hairy cumin contains most of them. The composition of the terpene hydrocarbons is mostly affected by roasting and significant increase or decrease of newly generated compounds was found. Alpha-pinene content changes from 1.6% to 16% in raw and roasted seeds respectively. In present study cumin is roasted as it is prepared in Indian kitchen. Pyrazines are generated normally after roasting¹⁵. It is evidenced by Hairy cumin raw where pyrazine is absent but trace amount is found in roasted condition. Due to the volatility of cumene compound 16.18% is lowered to 0.5% in roasted condition. Gama-terpinene, benzene are in higher content in roasted seeds than the raw ones. 16.18% cumene, 27% careen and 18% phellandrene and 4.2% coumarin are virtually lost during roasting as evident from GC MS study. 16% beta pinene, 31% 2,6,6-trimethylbicycloheptane and 17% dihydromyrcene is developed after roasting. In case of Cumin 1 cultivar of Rajasthan

Linalool is present in highest percentage (55.48%) and pyrazine at an appreciable amount (13.81%) in raw condition. In both the cases the compounds are not eluted in roasted condition.

Percentage of careen is in trace amount in the three cultivars of cumin seeds after roasting. It may be due to polymerization of the molecule. Both the Rajasthan varieties contain cumin aldehyde in very low quantity (Tables 1 and 2). Coumarin is present in all cultivars but it has increased in roast condition in Cumin 1 of Rajasthan and West Bengal variety.

Table 1. Some of the aroma compounds present in raw and roasted Hairy cumin cultivar of Rajasthan obtained from GC MS study

Sl. no.	Retention time	Compounds	Mol. weight	Raw (% w/w)	Roast (% w/w)
1.	5.05	Alpha-pinene	136	1.33	16
2.	5.62	Cumene	136	16.22	0.5
3.	6.08	Unknown	136.23	-	16
4.	6.39	3-Carene	136	27	6.37
5.	6.88	Pyrazine	124	-	3.83
6.	7.03	Beta-pinene	136	29	-
7.	7.43	Myrcene	136	-	1.80
8.	9.06	Hexanoic acid	130	Tr	-
9.	9.86	Alpha-phellandrene	136.23	18.34	0.50
10.	10.49	Gama-carene	136	-	Tr
11.	11.40	Alpha-terpinene	136	2.75	Tr
12.	11.60	Gama-terpinene	136	Tr	4.17
13.	12.90	Pyrazine (3-methyl-2-isobutyl-)	150	-	31
14.	13	Dihydromyrcene	138	-	-
15.	13.72	Benzene	148	Tr	13.21
16.	14.82	Didodecylphthalate	149	-	1.3
17.	15.57	Benzaldehyde	136	-	2.75
18.	16.07	Cuminaldehyde	148.20	-	0.36
19.	16.86	Thymol	192.25	Tr	0.53
20.	20.44	Hydrocimanyl acetate	-	-	8.78
21.	26.69	Unknown	122.12	Tr	1.63
22.	33.30	Coumarin (4-hydroxy)	162	4.2	-

GCMS result supports that Hairy cumin contains most of the essential oil. The composition of the terpene hydrocarbons is mostly affected by roasting and significant increase or decreases of newly generated compounds are found in tables.

Table 2. Some of the aroma compounds present in raw and roasted Cumin 1 cultivar of Rajasthan obtained from GC MS study

Sl. no.	Retention time	Compounds	Mol weight	Raw (% w/w)	Roast (% w/w)
1.	6.08	Beta-pinene	136.23	Tr	-
2.	6.88	Pyrazine	124	13.81	3.4
3.	7.63	<i>o</i> -Cymene	134	13.42	-
4.	8.16	Unknown	-	7.65	-
5.	10.33	Alpha-phellandrene	136.23	Tr	-
6.	11.07	<i>p</i> -Cymene	134.22	-	48
7.	11.34	Linalool	154	55.48	-
8.	11.75	Gama-terpinene	136.23	2.4	0.73
9.	15.56	Cumin-aldehyde	148.20	Tr	Tr
10.	30.12	Menth-8-one-3-ol	154.24	-	15
11.	33.93	Coumarin	-	7.22	31

Table 3. Some of the aroma compounds present in raw and roasted Cumin cultivar of West Bengal obtained from GC MS study

Sl. no.	Retention time	Compounds	Mol weight	Raw (% w/w)	Roast (% w/w)
1.	6.83	3-Carene	136	10	Tr
2.	7.63	<i>o</i> -Cymene	134	24	8.7
3.	8.22	Cineole (may be)	154.24	22.19	9.03
4.	11.14	<i>p</i> -Cymene	134.22	27	42.70
5.	11.80	Gama-terpinene	136.22	14	16.62
6.	33.77	Coumarin	146.14	1.9	22.91

SEM analysis of three samples are executed because the oil glands of the elongated mericarp structures (Fig. 1a) are responsible for the emergence of essential oil¹⁴. The outer architectural structure of the raw and roasted material is viewed more or less same. In raw Hairy cumin pappilose hairs are long and seat of these are connected with assemblage of canals (shown in the figures of $\times 300$). The pappilose hairs of Cumin 1 of Rajasthan are shorter and the canal mouths are less wider (Fig. 2b) than the Hairy cumin (Fig. 1b). Balagarh cultivar shows shorter and less number of pappilose hairs with inconspicuous assemblage of canals (Fig. 3b). These regions including the pappilose hairs are responsible for emergence of aroma. The macro and micro structures of the same species under the same genus differs prominently but the changes are slight between the raw and roasted samples. Due to roasting the pappilose hairs¹¹ between ridges and furrows become stiff than flexibility of the raw ones. After

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Full view of raw seed of Hairy cumin (a) showing long pappilose hairs (b).

roasting some of the pappilose hairs and assemblage of canals are destroyed and oil globules are spread through the inner side of the seeds which may help to release the beautiful aroma. It is clear from the above study that micro morphological structures may relate with emergence of essential oil. The present study establishes the fact that the agronomical factors especially soil characteristics play an important role in the productivity of cumin seeds as well as in the essential oil contents and composition. Some new components are identified in the aromatic

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Full view of raw seed of Cumin I of Rajasthan (a) showing short papillose hairs (b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Full view of raw seed of Cumin of West Bengal (a) showing short papillose hairs (b).

oils of the cumin seeds growing in different states. Effect of roasting of cumin seeds brings out distinct change both in microstructures and composition of aromatic oil.

Experimental

Procurement of sample : Dry samples of two cultivars of Indian cumin known as Hairy cumin and Cumin I of Rajasthan were collected from Gujarat Agriculture University, Jagudan, Gujarat, India. Third cultivar was collected from Seed Collection Centre, Department of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal, Hooghly.

Isolation of aromatic oil : 10 g of seeds of each of the three cultivars were cleaned and ground separately to make half dust in raw condition. 5 g of them were trans-

ferred in an ultraclean tightly capped glass container containing HPLC grade petroleum ether (40–60 °C)¹⁵. Other 5 g were heated for 3 min at 60 °C in a glass container kept on an oven. The roasted spices were cooled and capped immediately. Then the spices were dipped within the same solvent and kept as such for five hour and both of them were stirred gently for last one and half hour. The extracts were then collected in a small vial for GCMS analysis to ascertain the oil composition.

Authentic chemicals : The standard chemicals α -pinene (98% pure) and 3-carene (90% pure) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Inc., St. Luis, USA. Linalool was procured from Fluka Analytical, CH-9471 Buchs, Switzerland. All other chemicals were used of AR grade and

procured from Spectrochem Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

Analysis of aromatic oil : Analyses of the aromatic oils were carried out using a THERMOFISHER 5890 model series II, operating in EI mode at 70 eV, equipped with a splitless injector (240 °C). Helium was used as carrier gas (1 mL/min), and the capillary column was a HP 5 (30 cm × 0.25 mm; film thickness, 0.25 µm). The temperature was programmed as 50–220 °C at 10 °C/min and up to 235 °C at the rate of 5 °C/min. MS analysis of individual compounds was performed by matching their retention indices (RIs) and mass spectral range was from 0 to 300 *m/z*.

Separated compounds obtained from GC were identified from the recorded mass spectra and compared with the NIST library, authentic chemicals and Adams¹⁶.

SEM analysis of the seed : The samples were well dried in harvesting period and gold coating was not needed. Roasting was done on the same day as stated earlier and cooled samples were placed on stubs for Scanning Electron Microscopy¹¹. At 15 KV accelerating voltage the samples were examined under the SEM Quanta200 MK2 of FEI with appropriate magnification.

Above experimental procedures were repeated three times.

Acknowledgement

The financial support received from DST, Government of West Bengal is gratefully acknowledged. The first author likes to acknowledge the support received from Professor T. P. Sinha, Scientist-in-charge, Main Campus, SAIF, Bose Institute. Support received from Mr. S. R. Maji in GC-MS analysis and Mr. S. C. Maikap in SEM analysis is also thankfully acknowledged. We are thankful to Mr. M. R. Bhattacharya, Department of

Agriculture, Government of West Bengal and Dr. A. Sen, Ex-Head, USIC, University of Calcutta for their help in collection of the seeds.

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